
The Performance of the Regional Regulation Formation Body of the Regional House of Representatives in Drafting Regional Regulations in Bojonegoro Regency: A Case Study of the Dprd Secretariat of the Bojonegoro Regency

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the performance of the Regional Regulation Formation Body (Badan Pembentukan Peraturan Daerah/Bapemperda) of the Bojonegoro Regency Regional House of Representatives (DPRD) in drafting regional regulations during the 2020 legislative year. Employing a qualitative descriptive approach, the research analyzes legislative performance using six indicators proposed by Robbins and Judge (2009): quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, independence, and work commitment. Data were collected through in-depth interviews with key informants, documentation analysis, and non-participant observation, and were analyzed using an interactive qualitative analysis model. The findings indicate that Bapemperda's legislative performance had not reached an optimal level, particularly in terms of output quantity and timeliness, as only 12 out of 23 planned draft regional regulations were successfully enacted in 2020. While the quality of enacted regulations was generally adequate and supported by procedural compliance and coordination with the executive branch, performance was constrained by weak time management, limited member independence, and inconsistent work discipline. In addition, external factors, including the COVID-19 pandemic and dependency on higher-level regulations, further reduced legislative effectiveness. Overall, the study demonstrates that both institutional capacity and situational constraints significantly shaped the performance of regional regulation drafting in Bojonegoro Regency.

KEYWORDS: Legislative Performance, Bapemperda, Regional Regulations, DPRD, Regional Autonomy, Public Sector Performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The performance of public institutions is a fundamental element in realizing effective governance that is responsive to the needs of the community. Performance is measured not only by the implementation of administrative activities but also by the extent to which policy outputs have a real impact on the public interest, whether through regulations, programs, or services (Ishak, 2022; Pierre et al., 2024; Salomo & Rahmayanti, 2023). In the context of regional government, performance has a strategic position in line with the implementation of decentralization through regional autonomy policies that give broad authority to regional governments to regulate and manage government affairs in accordance with the characteristics of their regions (Budijaya & Heryanto, 2024; Samsidar, 2025; Sinaga & Damayanti, 2025).

The implementation of regional autonomy requires the presence of institutional mechanisms capable of formulating local policies effectively, particularly through the establishment of regional regulations (perda) as legal instruments that regulate regional governance and development (Sinaga & Damayanti, 2025). Within the structure of regional government, the Regional Representative Council (DPRD) plays a central role in the regional legislative process through its function of establishing regional regulations, which is carried out in partnership with the regional government as an equal partner. This function aims to ensure that every policy produced reflects the aspirations of the community and is in line with the principles of democracy and public accountability (Harita et al., 2026; Hariyanto et al., 2025; Syaori et al., 2025; Tuasikal & Homer, 2024).

To support the implementation of this legislative function, the DPRD formed the Regional Regulation Formation Agency (Bapemperda) as a permanent organ responsible for planning, drafting, harmonizing, and evaluating draft regional regulations (Annasruh et al., 2023; Rahmat, 2025). Bapemperda has strategic authority in drafting the Regional Regulation Formation Program (Propemperda) as an annual regional legislation roadmap that contains a list of priority regional regulations to be discussed and

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passed. The success of Propemperda is an important indicator in assessing the DPRD's legislative performance because it reflects the consistency between policy planning and the realization of regional legal products (Aulia, 2025; Mansur et al., 2025).

However, in practice, the performance of DPRD legislation often faces various challenges, whether structural, administrative, or political. One of the issues that often arises is the discrepancy between the number of planned legislative programs and the number of local regulations successfully completed in a single fiscal period (Rahmat, 2025; Surana, 2025). This phenomenon indicates a gap between normative planning and the implementation of legislative policies at the regional level.

This condition also occurred in the Bojonegoro Regency DPRD's Bapemperda in 2020. Based on Propemperda data, there were 23 draft regional regulations planned to be discussed and passed in one fiscal year. However, by the end of the year, only 12 regional regulations had been successfully completed, while 11 others remained unfinished. This reality indicates that the performance of regional legislation is still below the institutionally set targets.

The failure to achieve these targets is increasingly important to examine, given that regional regulations are the main instruments for regulating various strategic sectors, such as education, the regional economy, culture, regional taxation, and governance. The list of local regulations that were successfully passed in 2020 shows the dominance of regulations of an administrative and regional financial nature, while a number of other strategic agendas have not been optimally realized. This has the potential to affect the effectiveness of regional development and the quality of public services.

From the perspective of public organization performance management, Robbins & Judge (2009) define performance as the result of evaluating the work of individuals or organizations compared to predetermined standards or criteria. Robbins & Judge put forward six key performance indicators, namely quality of work, quantity of output, timeliness of completion, effectiveness of resource utilization, independence in task implementation, and commitment to the organization. The application of these indicators to the performance of the Bojonegoro Regency DPRD's Bapemperda shows weaknesses, particularly in terms of the quantity of legislation produced and the consistency of the completion of the legislative program according to the annual plan. Although the quality of several local regulations is considered quite good, the low level of Propemperda realization indicates that the legislative function is not yet running optimally.

In addition, the findings reveal that there are a number of inhibiting factors that affect the performance of Bapemperda, including the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has limited face-to-face activities, the ineffective determination of priorities for discussing local regulations, and the interdependence of regulations, which delays the further legislative process (Pangaribuan, 2022). Although the pandemic is a significant external obstacle, technological developments and remote work mechanisms should be used as adaptive strategies to maintain institutional productivity.

Previous studies have examined the performance of regional legislative councils (DPRD), particularly the Regional Regulation Formation Body (Bapemperda), in formulating local regulations. Research in Brebes Regency indicates that Bapemperda's performance has not been optimal due to limited consideration of strategic public interests (Permana & Warsudi, 2021), while similar findings in the Special Region of Yogyakarta highlight inconsistencies in the execution of Bapemperda's institutional responsibilities (Ginting, 2018). In contrast, research in Sampang Regency reports relatively adequate legislative performance in issue-specific regulation advocacy (Zakaria, 2021). Despite adopting qualitative descriptive approaches, these studies predominantly focus on supervisory, budgeting, or issue-specific legislative functions, leaving the strategic role and overall performance of Bapemperda in regional regulatory formulation insufficiently explored. This gap is critical, given that the effectiveness of regional regulation formation significantly determines the quality of public policy at the local level. Therefore, this study addresses the limited empirical understanding of Bapemperda's performance, the challenges it faces, and its implications for the achievement of regional legislative programs by applying Robbins and Judge's performance theory to the case of DPRD Bojonegoro.

Based on this background, this study aims to analyze the performance of the Bojonegoro Regency DPRD Regional Regulation Formation Agency in drafting regional regulations in 2020, with a focus on Propemperda achievements and the inhibiting factors that affect the effectiveness of regional legislative functions. The results of this study are expected to contribute conceptually to public administration studies and serve as practical evaluation material for improving the performance of DPRD legislation at the regional level.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative descriptive research design aimed at comprehensively examining the performance of the Regional Regulation Formation Body (Badan Pembentukan Peraturan Daerah/Bapemperda) of the Bojonegoro Regional House of Representatives (DPRD) in the formulation of local regulations. Qualitative descriptive research is appropriate for capturing institutional processes, meanings, and performance dynamics as they occur in real governance contexts without hypothesis testing (Creswell, 2014). The focus of this research is the performance of Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro in drafting regional regulations. Performance is analyzed using Robbins & Judge's (2009) performance theory, which conceptualizes performance through six

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indicators: quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, independence, and work commitment. These indicators are used as analytical lenses to assess how Bapemperda carries out its legislative roles and responsibilities.

Primary data were obtained from key informants directly involved in the regional regulation drafting process. Informants were selected using purposive sampling, based on their institutional position, authority, and knowledge relevant to the research objectives (Sugiyono, 2022). This technique enables in-depth exploration of governance practices from actors most familiar with the legislative process.

Table 1. Classification of Research Informants

No	Informant Position	Institutional Role
1	Chairperson of Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro	Key policymaker and coordinator of regional regulation drafting
2	Head of Session and Legislation Division	Administrative and technical oversight of legislative procedures
3	Head of Legislation Sub-Division	Technical drafting and documentation of regional regulations

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Data collection was conducted through multiple qualitative techniques to ensure data richness and triangulation:

1. In-depth interviews with selected informants to explore perceptions, experiences, and institutional challenges in the regulation drafting process.
2. Documentation analysis, including regional regulation drafts, meeting minutes, legislative programs (Propemperda), and relevant legal documents.
3. Non-participant observation to examine legislative activities, attendance patterns, and coordination processes within Bapemperda.

The combination of these techniques strengthens data credibility and allows cross-validation of findings (Yin, 2018).

Data analysis followed the interactive model of Miles et al. (2014), consisting of data collection, data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. Data reduction was carried out by coding and categorizing interview transcripts and documents according to the six performance indicators. The analyzed data were then systematically interpreted by linking empirical findings with relevant theories and previous studies to ensure analytical rigor. To enhance trustworthiness, this study applied data triangulation across interviews, observations, and documents. Peer debriefing and continuous reflection during analysis were also employed to minimize researcher bias and improve interpretive accuracy (Creswell & Poth, 2017).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Quality of Performance

Performance quality reflects the extent to which work outputs meet expected standards and demonstrate responsibility, accuracy, and professionalism (Robbins & Judge, 2009). In this study, the quality of Bapemperda’s performance is examined through members’ ability to carry out their legislative duties, discipline in work processes, and the substantive quality of draft regional regulations produced.

Empirical data indicate that the quality of Bapemperda members’ performance was generally assessed as good, although several aspects still require improvement. This assessment is reflected in the evaluation provided by the Chair of Bapemperda, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Assessment of Bapemperda Performance by the Chairperson

No	Performance Indicator	Performance Rating
1	Quality of work output and member discipline	B
2	Quantity of legislative output	C
3	Timeliness in task completion	C
4	Effectiveness in drafting regulations	B
5	Work independence	B
6	Work commitment	A

Source: Interview with the Chairperson of the Bapemperda of the Bojonegoro Regency DPRD, processed by the researchers (2026)

Note: A = Very Good; B = Good; C = Fair

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The table shows that the quality of work output and discipline of Bapemperda members received a “Good” (B) rating. This indicates that, from the leadership’s perspective, members are generally capable of fulfilling their roles in the drafting of regional regulations, although performance has not yet reached an optimal level.

This assessment is supported by interview data with the Chair of Bapemperda, who stated:

“In my view, the quality of Bapemperda members’ performance is generally good. There are still some issues that need improvement, but they remain within reasonable limits. One aspect that needs attention is work discipline, as there are occasions when members arrive late or are unable to attend meetings. In terms of legal knowledge, however, the members’ understanding is already quite adequate.”

This statement suggests that while members possess sufficient substantive knowledge to engage in legislative drafting, discipline-related issues—particularly attendance and punctuality—continue to affect the overall quality of performance.

Further insights were provided by the Head of the Session and Legislation Division of the DPRD Secretariat, who emphasized the procedural and institutional aspects of quality:

“From the Secretariat’s perspective, Bapemperda carries out its duties through clearly defined stages, starting from initial discussions to final enactment. The Secretariat facilitates coordination and technical processes to ensure that the drafting of regional regulations follows the required procedures. Throughout these stages, both the executive and legislative branches provide input so that the resulting regulations can be effectively used by the community.”

This explanation highlights that, procedurally, the drafting process has met formal standards, supported by coordination between the DPRD and the executive branch. However, procedural compliance alone does not automatically translate into optimal performance quality if discipline and consistency among members remain uneven.

Field observations conducted at the DPRD Secretariat further corroborate these findings. The researcher observed that although meetings and drafting activities were regularly scheduled, variations in member attendance and punctuality occasionally disrupted the continuity of discussions, potentially affecting the refinement and completeness of draft regulations.

According to Robbins and Judge (2009), performance quality is closely linked to the extent to which tasks are carried out accurately, responsibly, and in accordance with established standards. The findings of this study show that Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro has achieved an acceptable level of performance quality, particularly in terms of members’ legal understanding and compliance with formal legislative procedures; however, recurring issues related to work discipline indicate that this quality has not yet reached its full potential. This condition reflects a gap between technical competence and behavioral consistency, where members are able to produce substantively sound draft regulations, but weaknesses in discipline—such as irregular attendance and delays—undermine overall performance outcomes. Consistent with Robbins and Judge’s framework, improving performance quality therefore requires not only the strengthening of individual competencies but also the reinforcement of discipline, accountability mechanisms, and performance management within Bapemperda, supported by structured capacity-building programs and internal performance Supervision.

2) Quantity of Performance

Quantity of performance refers to the amount of work output produced by organizational members in relation to predetermined performance targets (Robbins & Judge, 2009). In this study, the quantity of Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro’s performance is measured by comparing the number of draft regional regulations planned in the 2020 Regional Legislative Program (*Program Pembentukan Peraturan Daerah/Propemperda*) with the number of regulations successfully enacted within the same year. As shown in Table 3, Bapemperda targeted the formulation of 23 draft regional regulations in 2020, encompassing various policy sectors such as social protection, regional enterprises, spatial planning, taxation, and budgeting.

Table 3. Regional Legislative Program (Propemperda) of Bojonegoro Regency, 2020

No.	Title of Draft Regional Regulation
1	Draft Regional Regulation on the Protection and Fulfillment of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities
2	Draft Regional Regulation on Village-Owned Enterprises
3	Draft Regional Regulation on the Implementation of Manpower Affairs
4	Draft Regional Regulation on the Protection and Empowerment of Farmers
5	Draft Regional Regulation on Entertainment
6	Draft Regional Regulation on Industrial Estate Development
7	Draft Regional Regulation on the Administration of Education
8	Draft Regional Regulation on the Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 13 of 2016 concerning the Formation and Structure of Regional Government Agencies of Bojonegoro Regency
9	Draft Regional Regulation on the Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 27 of 2011 concerning the Limited Liability Company Griya Dharma Kusuma

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10	Draft Regional Regulation on the Second Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 5 of 2006 concerning the Establishment of the Regional-Owned Enterprise PT Bangkit Bangun Sarana
11	Draft Regional Regulation on the Second Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 19 of 1990 concerning the Establishment of the Regional Drinking Water Company of Bojonegoro Regency
12	Draft Regional Regulation on the Amendment to the Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2011 concerning the Use of Regional Assets
13	Draft Regional Regulation on the Amendment to the Regional Regulation Number 20 of 2011 concerning Business Service Retribution
14	Draft Regional Regulation on the Third Amendment to the Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 14 of 2011 concerning Rural and Urban Land and Building Tax
15	Draft Regional Regulation on the Spatial Plan of Bojonegoro Regency 2020–2040
16	Draft Regional Regulation on the Establishment of a New Regional-Owned Enterprise Engaged in the Management of a 10% Participating Interest
17	Draft Regional Regulation on the Establishment of a New Regionally Owned Enterprise Engaged in Gas Management
18	Draft Regional Regulation on the Establishment of a New Regionally Owned Enterprise Engaged in the Agricultural Sector
19	Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget for Fiscal Year 2021
20	Amendment to the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget for Fiscal Year 2019
21	Accountability Report on the Implementation of the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget for Fiscal Year 2019
22	Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 13 of 2015 concerning Village Heads
23	Draft Regional Regulation on the Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2010 concerning Regional Taxes

Source: DPRD Secretariat of Bojonegoro Regency, processed by the researchers (2026)

However, the empirical data in Table 4 indicate that only 12 regional regulations were successfully enacted in 2020, meaning approximately 52% of the planned legislative output was realized.

Table 4. Enacted Regional Regulations of Bojonegoro Regency, 2020

No.	Year	Title of Regional Regulation
1	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 1 of 2020 on the Preservation of Traditional Arts
2	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 2 of 2020 on the Development and Protection of Cooperatives and Micro Enterprises
3	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 3 of 2020 on the Revocation of Regional Regulation Number 25 of 2011 concerning Mandatory Taxpayer Registration
4	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 4 of 2020 on the Tourism Development Master Plan of Bojonegoro Regency for the Period 2019–2025
5	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 5 of 2020 on the Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 13 of 2016 concerning the Formation and Structure of Regional Government Agencies
6	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 6 of 2020 on the Accountability for the Implementation of the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget for Fiscal Year 2019
7	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 7 of 2020 on the Amendment to the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget for Fiscal Year 2020
8	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 8 of 2020 on the Administration of Education
9	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 9 of 2020 on the Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2011 concerning Retribution for the Use of Regional Assets
10	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 10 of 2020 on the Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 20 of 2011 concerning Business Service Retribution
11	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 11 of 2020 on the Third Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 14 of 2011 concerning Rural and Urban Land and Building Tax
12	2020	Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 12 of 2020 on the Amendment to Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2010 concerning Regional Taxes

Source: JDIH Bojonegoro Regency (2020)

Interview findings further clarify the factors contributing to this gap between planned and realized outputs. The Chair of Bapemperda stated that the legislative targets were not fully achieved due to several constraints, particularly external disruptions and procedural dependencies:

“In terms of quantity, Bapemperda members were unable to fully achieve the planned targets. This was influenced by several inhibiting factors, especially the COVID-19 pandemic, which limited face-to-face meetings. In addition, some draft regulations

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could not be finalized because they depended on higher-level regulations that were still under discussion, so their completion had to be postponed to the following year.”

Similarly, the Head of the Session and Legislation Division of the DPRD Secretariat emphasized issues related to readiness and coordination in the legislative process:

“Several draft regulations were not yet ready for finalization and therefore accumulated into the next legislative session. Some discussions required a longer deliberation process, while others had to be postponed because related higher-level regulations had not yet been enacted.”

These interview results indicate that the shortfall in legislative output was caused not only by the extraordinary conditions of the pandemic but also by internal and structural challenges, including delays in regulatory harmonization and limited preparedness of draft regulations.

According to Robbins & Judge (2009), performance quantity reflects the volume of outputs produced within a specific timeframe relative to established targets. The findings demonstrate that Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro’s quantitative performance in 2020 was below expectations, as nearly half of the planned legislative agenda was not completed within the year. While external factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic significantly disrupted legislative activities, the persistence of unfinished draft regulations and reliance on unresolved higher-level policies indicate underlying weaknesses in planning realism, coordination, and legislative management. From a performance perspective, this condition suggests that improving quantitative performance requires not only adaptive responses to external shocks but also stronger internal scheduling, better preparation of draft regulations, and enhanced coordination across institutional levels to ensure that legislative targets can be achieved as planned.

3) Timeliness of Performance

Timeliness refers to the extent to which tasks are completed within predetermined schedules and deadlines, serving as a key indicator of work discipline and performance effectiveness (Robbins & Judge, 2009). In the context of regional regulation drafting, Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro is institutionally required to complete its legislative agenda in accordance with annual targets established in the Regional Legislative Program (Program Pembentukan Peraturan Daerah/Propemperda). As shown in Table 5, the 2020 Propemperda consisted of various types of draft regulations, with newly proposed regulations dominating.

Table 5. Types of Regional Legislative Programs (Propemperda) in Bojonegoro Regency, 2020

No	Type of Draft Regulation	Number
1	New Draft Regulations	14
2	Amendments	9
3	Revocations	–
	Total	23

Source: DPRD Secretariat of Bojonegoro Regency, processed by the researchers (2026)

Despite the planned targets, empirical findings show that Bapemperda was only able to finalize 12 out of 23 draft regional regulations in 2020, leaving 11 regulations unfinished and carried over to subsequent years. Interview data indicate that delays were a recurring issue. The Chair of Bapemperda acknowledged that legislative targets were not completed on schedule, emphasizing the need for improved time management:

“We were not able to complete the formation of regional regulations within the planned timeframe. In my view, this indicates the need to strengthen time management, because completing tasks on schedule would reduce workload pressure and allow members to work more effectively.”

Similarly, the Head of the Session and Legislation Division of the DPRD Secretariat explained that delays were often caused by substantive and procedural factors beyond administrative control:

“From the Secretariat’s side, timeliness cannot be determined unilaterally. Delays often occur because new materials emerge during deliberations, requiring additional data and extended discussion time before a draft regulation can be finalized.”

Field observations further confirmed that legislative timelines frequently extended beyond planned schedules, while data management challenges within the Secretariat—such as staff rotation and limited archival continuity—also hindered timely access to supporting documents.

According to Robbins & Judge (2009), timeliness reflects the extent to which work activities are completed by established deadlines and schedules. The findings of this study indicate that Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro’s timeliness performance in 2020 fell below expectations, as nearly half of the planned legislative agenda was not completed within the designated year. While external and substantive factors—such as evolving regulatory materials and complex deliberation processes—contributed to these delays, the persistence of unmet deadlines also points to weaknesses in time management, workflow coordination, and institutional data

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management. From a performance perspective, improving timeliness requires not only adaptive legislative planning but also stronger scheduling discipline, better documentation systems, and enhanced coordination between legislative members and the supporting Secretariat to ensure that regulatory targets can be completed within the intended timeframe.

4) Effectiveness of Performance

Effectiveness refers to the extent to which organizational activities achieve predetermined goals and targets, reflecting the organization’s capacity to transform inputs into desired outcomes (Robbins & Judge, 2009). In this study, the effectiveness of the Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro is assessed based on its ability to carry out the regional regulation drafting process in line with planned objectives, despite various constraints encountered in 2020.

Empirical findings indicate that while legislative activities continued, their effectiveness was not fully optimal. Interview data with the Chair of Bapemperda reveal that legislative performance was generally considered sufficiently effective in terms of planning, yet outcomes fell short of expectations due to external disruptions, particularly the COVID-19 pandemic: *“In terms of effectiveness, the work was fairly effective and followed the planned schedule; however, the targets were not fully achieved because several obstacles emerged, especially the COVID-19 pandemic, which limited members’ ability to conduct meetings and legislative discussions.”* This view is reinforced by the Head of the Session and Legislation Division of the DPRD Secretariat, who emphasized that pandemic-related restrictions significantly altered working mechanisms: *“During 2020, effectiveness was inevitably affected by health restrictions. Meetings were conducted through teleconferencing facilitated by the Secretariat to ensure that Bapemperda’s duties continued, but virtual meetings limited interaction, particularly in terms of discussion and question-and-answer sessions, which are usually more effective in face-to-face settings.”* These findings are consistent with field observations and documentary evidence, which identified several key factors hindering effectiveness, as summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Factors Constraining Bapemperda Performance Effectiveness in 2020

No	Constraining Factors
1	COVID-19 pandemic and mobility restrictions
2	Prioritization of specific draft regulations
3	Dependency on unresolved higher-level regulations
4	Limited interaction and discussion during meetings

Source: DPRD Secretariat of Bojonegoro Regency (2020)

Figure 1. Working Visit Meeting Activities of the Regional Regulation Formation Body (Bapemperda) of the Bojonegoro Regency DPRD

Source: DPRD Secretariat of Bojonegoro Regency (2020)

Taken together, these findings indicate that although institutional mechanisms such as remote working arrangements enabled legislative activities to continue, the overall effectiveness of Bapemperda’s performance was constrained by reduced interaction quality, regulatory dependencies, and shifting policy priorities. According to Robbins & Judge (2009), effectiveness is achieved

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when organizational outputs align with established goals and expectations; therefore, the inability to fully realize legislative targets despite ongoing activities reflects a partial effectiveness gap. This gap suggests that while adaptive strategies—such as teleconferencing and work-from-home systems—helped sustain operations during the pandemic, they were insufficient to fully substitute for direct deliberative processes essential to effective legislative performance. Strengthening digital governance capacity, improving deliberation mechanisms, and enhancing coordination between legislative actors are thus crucial to improving Effectiveness in similar crisis contexts.

5) Independence of Members' Performance

Independence is a key performance indicator that reflects the maturity of organizational members in carrying out tasks responsibly, proactively, and in accordance with predetermined targets without the need for continuous supervision from superiors (Robbins & Judge, 2009). In Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro, independence is expected to support timely and effective legislative performance. However, the findings indicate that member independence has not yet been fully achieved. The Chair of Bapemperda stated that members still tend to rely on leadership direction, noting that *“member independence needs to be strengthened through the development of a discipline-oriented work culture, so that tasks can be completed without waiting for instructions from the leadership and can be finalized on time.”* Meanwhile, the Head of the Session and Legislation Division of the DPRD Secretariat emphasized that, from an institutional perspective, Bapemperda already possesses autonomous authority in executing its duties, explaining that *“Bapemperda inherently has the authority to perform its functions independently, and this authority is formally exercised.”* Nevertheless, field observations at the DPRD Secretariat reveal a gap between formal autonomy and actual work practices, as several members were still dependent on directives before initiating tasks (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro Regency Meeting Activities
Source: DPRD Secretariat of Bojonegoro Regency (2020)

From the perspective of Robbins & Judge (2009) performance theory, this condition indicates that structural independence alone is insufficient to ensure high performance if it is not accompanied by individual initiative and self-directed behavior. Consequently, limited behavioral independence among members may hinder performance effectiveness and delay legislative processes. Strengthening internal discipline, encouraging proactive work behavior, and reinforcing accountability mechanisms are therefore essential to enhance independence and improve the overall performance of Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro.

6) Work Commitment of Performance

Work commitment refers to the degree of an individual's psychological attachment to their work, reflected in loyalty to organizational goals, willingness to exert effort, and consistency in fulfilling work responsibilities, all of which significantly influence performance outcomes (Robbins & Judge, 2009). In the context of legislative performance, work commitment among Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro members is particularly important to ensure continuity in deliberations and timely completion of regional regulations. In this study, work commitment was operationalized through attendance levels during official legislative activities.

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Table 7. Attendance at Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro Activities (2020)

No	Activity	Attendance Rate
1	Bapemperda working meetings	90%
2	Plenary sessions	90%
3	Out-of-town working visits	90%

Source: DPRD Secretariat of Bojonegoro Regency, processed by researchers (2026)

As shown in Table 7, attendance rates across key legislative activities in 2020 averaged 90 percent, indicating a relatively high but not optimal level of work commitment. Interview findings support this assessment. The Chair of Bapemperda stated that “members generally demonstrate a fairly good level of work commitment,” suggesting that, at a normative level, commitment to legislative duties is present. Meanwhile, the Head of the Session and Legislation Division of the DPRD Secretariat emphasized that coordination between Bapemperda, the local government legal team, and the Secretariat has been routinely conducted, with the Secretariat facilitating draft preparation to ensure that proposed regulations are ready for submission and to prevent backlog in subsequent legislative years. Nevertheless, empirical evidence shows that several regional regulations planned for 2020 were not completed within the same year, indicating that attendance-based commitment did not fully translate into optimal legislative performance. Field observations further revealed that partial attendance during deliberative sessions sometimes disrupted the flow of discussion and delayed decision-making.

According to Robbins & Judge (2009), work commitment influences performance by shaping individuals’ willingness to consistently invest effort and take responsibility for achieving organizational targets. The findings of this study suggest that although Bapemperda DPRD Bojonegoro members demonstrate a moderate level of affective and normative commitment, this commitment has not been fully internalized into consistent work behavior and performance outcomes. The absence of full attendance and the postponement of several draft regulations indicate a gap between formal commitment and actual task completion. From a performance perspective, strengthening work commitment requires reinforcing discipline, responsibility, and ownership of legislative targets so that commitment is reflected not only in attendance rates but also in sustained effort, continuity of deliberations, and timely completion of regional regulations.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings indicate that Bapemperda’s legislative performance has not yet reached an optimal level, particularly in terms of the quantity of output and the timeliness of completion, as only 12 out of 23 draft regional regulations planned in the Regional Legislative Program (Propemperda) were successfully enacted within the designated year. Although the quality of the enacted regulations was generally acceptable and supported by adequate legal understanding, procedural compliance, and coordination between the legislative and executive branches, performance weaknesses were evident in the consistency of work discipline, scheduling, and completion of legislative targets. The effectiveness of performance was further constrained by the COVID-19 pandemic, which limited face-to-face deliberations and reduced the quality of interaction during virtual meetings, while institutional dependence on unresolved higher-level regulations delayed several draft laws. In addition, member independence remained limited, as legislative activities often relied on leadership direction rather than proactive individual initiative, and although work commitment appeared relatively high based on attendance rates, this commitment did not consistently translate into sustained productivity or timely legislative outcomes. From a theoretical perspective, these findings reveal a gap between technical competence and behavioral consistency, where formal authority, legal expertise, and participation are not fully accompanied by strong time management, accountability, and performance-oriented work practices, as emphasized in Robbins and Judge’s performance theory. This study is subject to several limitations, including its qualitative descriptive design with a limited number of informants, its focus on a single legislative year characterized by extraordinary pandemic conditions, and its reliance on institutional perspectives without incorporating broader stakeholder or public evaluations of regulatory impacts. Therefore, future research is recommended to adopt comparative and longitudinal approaches across regions and legislative periods, integrate mixed methods to combine qualitative insights with quantitative performance indicators, and examine the influence of political dynamics, leadership styles, digital governance capacity, and policy outcomes to provide a more comprehensive understanding of legislative performance within decentralized governance systems.

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